

“Noble and meritorious”: formation and maintenance of scientific elites through the cultivating of scholarly personae

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When passing on the position of president of the Brazilian Academy of Sciences to Menezes de Oliveira in 1937, Alvaro Alberto da Mota e Silva praised his successor in the following way:

Not only as a man of science does Menezes de Oliveira ascend in admiration from his peers. The refined moral elegance, the aesthetic sense and the finesse of ‘gentleman’ harmoniously merge with natural modesty, underlined with an almost timidity, so often observed in the composition of elite scholars.

De Oliveira’s inauguration speech figured in the *Annals of the Brazilian Academy of Science*, following communications on South American scorpions, limit theory and Hindu philosophy.

What do scholarly journals tell us about elite formation in the past? Beyond the role of spreading scientific knowledge, science periodicals were also sites where scientists presented themselves to the scientific community.

In this paper, I propose the use of scholarly journals as historical sources for the study of scientific elites. Periodicals such as the *Annals of the Brazilian Academy of Science* contain rich portraits of scientific sociability stored in its paratexts. Conference reports, inauguration speeches and obituaries provide the researcher with insights into the formation and maintenance of a scientific elite. Therefore, I argue that scientific journals offer a unique view of how elite scientists carved, shaped and reinforced a scholarly persona.

Persona Studies are dedicated to the personal and collective expectations that lie behind the construction of a scientific or scholarly self, or persona. Niskanen, Bosch and Wils (2018 p.1) explain that scientific personae “are not just a mask or a role that individuals assume or shape and are shaped by. They are collective entities, a kind of cultural and social repertoires on how to be a person of science.” The successful

establishment of a scientific reputation requires more than research skills. It often includes the embodiment of a set of virtues (Paul 2014) and even moral values (Veit-Brause 2002).

In the paper I will present, I use the *Annals of the Brazilian Academy of Science* as primary sources of research. The *Annals* is the longest running scientific publication in the country, issued since 1929, and for this work I specifically focus on issues published between 1930 and 1939, as this was a crucial decade for the establishment of the Academy’s reputation. The institution was granted official recognition by the federal government as a public interest entity, and given financial support to maintain its publications, which allowed the Academy to expand its communication and exchange with other scientific institutions inside and outside the country. Academics (“Acadêmicos”, as the members were later to be known) took part in the creation of the first Brazilian universities, which reinforced their expert status.

The Brazilian Academy of Sciences was founded in 1916 by a group of professors from the Polytechnical School of Rio de Janeiro and later joined by scholars from other research institutes. The first members of the Academy were wealthy individuals that relied on personal resources, both social and financial, to pursue the main initial ambitions of the Society: the promotion and institutionalization of scientific research (Hey 2012).

The Brazilian Academy was embedded in strong positivistic influence. Hence, the embodiment of a mission to actively contribute to the progress of the nation was one of the traits that composed the ideal Academic. The Academics were not only expected to be remarkable men of science but they should also display a set of personal qualities that reflected and reinforced the importance of the Society and its self-claimed “elevated objective”. Former president Euzébio de Queiroz

for instance was celebrated among his peers for his “incomparable qualities of an energetic administrator and indefatigable and enlightened researcher” as much as his dedication to “hold our Academy in high esteem, the way it deserves to be esteemed”.

Lengthy obituaries were also published in the Annals of the Academy in honour of its most illustrious members, and made for an opportune space for persona reinforcement. Juliano Moreira, founding member and perpetual honorary president, was said to have brought to the association “those enchanting attributes of calm and tranquility, of benevolence and tolerance, of modesty and discretion, of love of work and moderation”.

The Academics’ dedication to curating themselves and the institution they represented a respectable reputation paid off. Occupying a chair at the select table of members has become the epitome of outstanding scientific performance. The Brazilian Academy of Sciences played a fundamental and successful role in the creation of government-funded initiatives (research funds, universities, research institutes) that expanded access to science to other social groups.

However, ethnic, gendered and regional (North versus South) discrepancies in scientific participation have characterized the composition of the Academy’s membership throughout its 107 years of existence (Hey and Rodrigues 2017).

Such discrepancies are among the objects of study of the GLOBAL ACADEMIES project, where the present work on persona building stems from. The Global Academies project is an ERC-funded project that will, in the course of 5 years, investigate the role of scientific societies in the globalization of science. The project hypothesizes that scientific societies acted as gatekeepers in the globalization of science, simultaneously opening up professionalized science to new groups and limiting (full) access through their activities. A team of 4 researchers working on 4 countries – Brazil, India, the United States and France – will scrutinize subtle codes of conduct as well as how gender, nationality and geopolitics potentially played a role in creating divisions within scientific groups¹.

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